

Graphical Model Lab: Towards the Development of Graphical Modelling Open Source SaaS

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1. Introduction

Graph has been a representation of several machine learning algorithms, e.g. probabilistic graphical model, neural network, etc. We are creating Open Source SaaS to facilitate the

experiments of graph based machine learning algorithms with Big Data.

We introduce this tool with various topics, including system architecture, two calculation models

(one parametric and one non-parametric) with arbitrary graph structure, and spark implementation for the algorithms.

Then, we show some demo for a simple classification task, using this tool.

2. Aim

To introduce Graphical Model Lab, an Open Source SaaS of Graphical Modelling Experiment Tool and show one parametric and one non parametric method for arbitrary graph structure with Spark Implementation.

3. Material and methods

Our demonstration is conducted on wine data from <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/machine-learning-databases/wine-quality/>. The goal of the task is to predict if a liquid is red or white wine, given chemical features. We evaluate one parametric model and one non parametric model for this dataset.

4. Results

The test has been done by 10 fold cross validation.

The parametric model gets roughly 98 ~ 99% accuracy. And, the non parametric model also get the similar result 98~99%. This result has been obtained from one specific graph structure.

We create and test several different kinds of graph structure in the demo, using the tool.

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5. Conclusions

We showed how users can conduct classification task experiments in a user friendly manner, using our tool. We could not show how Big Data existing in Web can help us to solve the problem in demo. But, we continue to work on improving the tool, e.g. developing graph structure search algorithm, integration of Big Data in Web, etc.

6. Keywords

Machine Learning; Artificial Intelligence; Graphical Model; Architecture; Spark; Scalability; Big Data

Author biography

Mao Ito has completed his M.S from University of Wisconsin Madison, U.S.A and B.S from Shimane University, Japan. He is passionate about data engineering and data science. He is running Graphical Model Lab community, Japan to create Open Source SaaS Graphical Modelling Tool.